

Exploring Solutions to the Odd-sized Grid Classification Problem in Cellular Automata.

Anna Nenca¹[0000-0003-2746-1061] and Barbara Wolnik^{2,3}[0000-0003-2935-5529]

¹ Institute of Informatics, Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Informatics,
University of Gdańsk, 80-308 Gdańsk, Poland

² Institute of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematics, Physics and Informatics,
University of Gdańsk, 80-308 Gdańsk, Poland

³ KERMIT, Department of Data Analysis and Mathematical Modelling, Faculty of
Bioscience Engineering, Ghent University, Coupure links 653, B-9000 Gent, Belgium

Abstract. We consider one-dimensional grids $\mathcal{G}_n = \{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$, (where n is a positive odd integer) with periodic boundary condition and with the state set $Q = \{0, 1\}$. We are interested in finding a local rule with the smallest possible radius that can correctly classify each initial configuration according to its parity.

Keywords: Cellular automata · parity problem · finite grid.

The parity problem is a challenge in cellular automata (CA) where the goal is to classify initial configurations into two classes based on their parity. If the initial configuration contains an odd number of 1s, the CA should converge to a fixed point of all 1s. Conversely, if the initial configuration contains an even number of 1s, the CA should converge to a fixed point of all 0s. This problem is considered more difficult than the density classification problem (DCP) because a simple flip in any input bit can alter the output.

However, the solution to the parity problem exists. In a paper by Betel et al. [1], they described a local rule called the BFO rule with a radius of 4 (neighborhood size of 9) that solves the parity problem. The construction of the BFO rule involved analyzing the properties of the De Bruijn graph of the rule, which preserves parity and converges correctly to a homogeneous configuration for any initial configuration.

The paper also demonstrated that no binary CA with a radius of at most two (neighborhood size not greater than 5) can solve the parity problem for all odd-sized grids. The question of whether a rule with a radius of 3 (neighborhood size of 7) exists to solve the parity problem remains open. The authors attempted to find such a rule using a sophisticated evolutionary algorithm.

We introduce new approach to the parity problem. A perfect solution needs to keep the parity of any configuration, thus it has to be number-conserving considered as a function in the field \mathbb{Z}_2 . Most tools used in the field of number conservation will be useful also in the area of the parity problem.

References

1. H. Betel, P. P. Oliveira, and P. Flocchini. Solving the parity problem in one-dimensional cellular automata. *Natural Computing: An International Journal*, 12(3):323–337, 2013.